

inoculum is prepared by soaking 10 g rice seed hulls in 30 ml normal saline solution for 2 h, then concentrating the solution to 10% of its original volume by centrifuging at 4,000 g for 20 min.

The percentage of varieties showing positive reaction by IRMA varied with origin (see table). The lowest was

47.4% and the highest 100% (all seeds were from a diseased area). In general, the majority of the seeds from diseased areas were more or less infected. The CI method was less sensitive than IRMA.

Similar results were obtained for disease-free seed samples by both

IRMA and CI methods. For diseased seed samples detected by IRMA, however, only 67% showed a positive reaction to the CI test. IRMA is a more effective and reliable seed inspection method. □

Physiochemical treatments to break dormancy in rice

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We studied the effects of three physiochemical treatments on breaking dormancy in rice, using 200 healthy seeds of IR36, IR34, and H4 per treatment. Two weeks after harvest in 1988, seeds were kept at 50 °C dry heat for 5 d, soaked 20 h in 0.1 N HNO₃ solution, or dehulled. Seeds germinated in petri dishes were counted 5 d after.

Germination varied among varieties and treatments (see table). IR34 could be considered a strongly dormant

Rice seed germination with different dormancy-breaking treatments. China, 1988.

Variety	Germination (%)				Mean ^a
	No treatment	50 °C dry heat	HNO ₃ soaking	Dehulled	
IR36	81	92	87	46	76.5 a
IR34	37	75	52	26	47.5 b
H4	84	97	88	86	88.0 a
Mean ^a	67.3 bc	88.0 a	75.7 ab	52.7 c	70.7

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by *t*-test

variety—only 37% of its untreated seeds germinated. With 50 °C dry heat treatment, 75% germinated; with soaking in HNO₃, 52% germinated. Germination in weakly dormant IR36 and H4 also was stimulated by the two methods. The dry heat method was significantly better than the no treatment.

Hull removal did not produce any better results than no treatment, perhaps because the dormancy factor (or germination inhibitor) may be in the seed coat rather than in the hull, or it could be due to mechanical injury to seeds during dehulling. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management – inorganic sources

Response of rice to pyrite topdressing at different fertilizer levels

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Pyrite contains 22-24% total sulfur, 20-22% Fe, 0.5-0.8% MgO, 0.1% CaO, 0.6-0.8% alumina, 35-40% silica, 2-3% C, 0.02% Zn, 0.05% Cu, and 0.01% Mn. We noticed farmers using pyrite on their rice crops. This led us to test six pyrite rates and one Zn application at three fertilizer levels. The treatments in a split-plot design with three replications are given in the table.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.5, EC (1:2) 0.09 dS/m, 0.42% organic C, 17.5 kg available P/ha, 135 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract), CEC 8.8

meq/100 g soil, 180 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), and 0.86 ppm available Zn (DTPA extractable).

Grain yield of rice with different fertilizer levels and pyrite topdressing at Masodha, Faisabad, India, 1985.

Fertilizer combination (NPK kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							Mean
	No pyrite	0.2 t/ha	0.4 t/ha	0.6 t/ha	0.8 t/ha	1.0 t/ha	5% ZnSO ₄ spray	
Low (60:13:25)	4.0	4.2	4.3	4.5	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3
Medium (80:18:33)	4.1	4.4	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.6	4.6
High (120:26:50)	4.4	4.8	5.0	5.0	5.1	5.3	5.1	5.0
Mean	4.2	4.4	4.6	4.7	4.7	4.8	4.7	
LSD (P =0.05)		Fertility 0.40		Pyrites 0.20				
CV (%)		4.66						